

A Symplectic-Linear Proof of the Gottesman–Knill Theorem

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Abstract

Quantum computing is interesting because it may help us solve some problems that are very hard for ordinary computers. In many of these problems, the difficulty grows very quickly as the system gets larger. So it is natural to think that quantum computations should in general be too complicated to simulate efficiently.

But this is not always true. Some quantum computations still have enough hidden structure to be simulated efficiently on a classical computer. This essay studies this surprising idea in a concrete setting. The main idea is that a problem that first looks impossibly large can become much simpler once it is rewritten in the right algebraic language.

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1 Introduction

Quantum computation is often seen as too hard to simulate on a classical computer. This seems natural: an n -qubit¹ pure state lives in a space of dimension 2^n , so writing down the state directly appears to require exponentially many numbers. From this point of view, it is natural to think that every quantum process should be hard to simulate on a classical computer.

The Gottesman–Knill theorem shows that this expectation is false. It shows that a large family of quantum circuits can still be simulated in polynomial time, rather than requiring exponential time.[1, p. 19][2, p. 2] The interesting question is therefore not simply whether a system is quantum, but what extra structure makes efficient classical simulation possible.

The aim of this essay is to prove the Gottesman–Knill theorem by translating the problem into linear algebra over \mathbb{F}_2 . After introducing the basic quantum notions, we encode Pauli operators by binary vectors, rewrite commutation in this language, and then use this description to give the proof.

2 Quantum computing preliminaries

Before turning to the symplectic formalism, we briefly introduce the quantum ingredients that it acts on. The aim is to explain only the notions that will later be translated into linear algebra: Pauli operators, measurement, commutation, and the gate set in the Gottesman–Knill theorem.

2.1 Quantum gates and the Pauli matrices

A quantum *gate* is represented by a *unitary operator* U on $(\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$ satisfying $U^\dagger U = I$.²[4, p. 15] The most basic single-qubit gates are the *Pauli matrices* (often written I, X, Y, Z). With respect to the basis $\{e_0, e_1\}$, called the *computational basis*, they are

$$I = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad X = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad Y = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad Z = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Equivalently, they are characterized by their action on basis:[2, p. 2]

$$Xe_0 = e_1, \quad Xe_1 = e_0; \quad Ze_0 = e_0, \quad Ze_1 = -e_1;$$

¹A qubit is modelled by the two-dimensional complex vector space \mathbb{C}^2 with standard basis vectors $e_0 = (1, 0)^\top$ and $e_1 = (0, 1)^\top$. So an n -qubit system is modelled by $(\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$.

²Throughout, A^\dagger denotes the conjugate transpose of a complex matrix A : if $A = (a_{ij})$, then $A^\dagger = (\overline{a_{ji}})$.

An n -qubit system is described by a complex Hilbert space³ $\mathcal{H} \cong (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n}$. A *Pauli operator* on such a system is an operator of the form:

$$P = P_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes P_n, \quad P_j \in \{I, X, Y, Z\} \text{ for each } j.$$

2.2 States, observables, and measurement

We now introduce the three basic notions needed later.

A pure *state* is represented by a unit vector $\psi \in \mathcal{H}$, where two unit vectors are taken to represent the same state if and only if they differ by multiplication by a phase factor $e^{i\theta}$ for some $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$. [4, p. 5]. In the rest of this essay, for brevity, we write “state” for “pure state”.

An *observable* is an operator M on \mathcal{H} satisfying $M = M^\dagger$; such an operator is called *Hermitian*. By the spectral theorem⁴ there is an orthogonal decomposition $M = \sum_\lambda \lambda \Pi_\lambda$, where Π_λ is the orthogonal projector onto the eigenspace $E_\lambda = \text{Ker}(M - \lambda I)$.

Pauli operators are Hermitian and unitary, so they can be used both as quantum gates and as observables. [4, pp. 5–6]

A (*projective*) *measurement* of an observable M on a state ψ is a process that produces an eigenvalue λ of M as an outcome and updates the state accordingly. This process is determined by the eigenspace decomposition of M . It need not be deterministic: if ψ has components in several eigenspaces of M , different outcomes can occur. The probability that the outcome is λ is $p(\lambda) = \|\Pi_\lambda \psi\|^2$, the squared length of the component of ψ lying in E_λ . If the outcome is λ , the state is updated by normalizing the projection onto E_λ :

$$\tilde{\psi} = \frac{\Pi_\lambda \psi}{\sqrt{p(\lambda)}} \quad (\text{defined when } p(\lambda) > 0).$$

In particular, if ψ is an eigenvector of M with eigenvalue λ , then $\Pi_\lambda \psi = \psi$, so $p(\lambda) = 1$ and the outcome is deterministic. [4, pp. 5–6]

2.3 Commutation

For operators A, B on a Hilbert space, the *commutator* is

$$[A, B] := AB - BA.$$

We say A and B *commute* if $[A, B] = 0$ (equivalently $AB = BA$).

³Here a complex Hilbert space means a finite-dimensional complex vector space with an inner product. Throughout this essay, all Hilbert spaces are finite-dimensional.

⁴In finite dimension, any Hermitian matrix can be written as a sum of its distinct eigenvalues times the orthogonal projections onto the corresponding eigenspaces.

Lemma 2.3.1 (Commuting Hermitian operators are simultaneously diagonalizable). *Let A, B be Hermitian operators on a finite-dimensional complex Hilbert space. If $AB = BA$, then there exists an orthonormal basis consisting of common eigenvectors of A and B .*[4, p. 6].

Proof. A proof is given in Appendix A. □

Thus, if A and B commute, there are states on which both observables have fixed outcomes. For Pauli operators, a direct calculation shows that the eigenvalues are ± 1 . Hence a single state can satisfy equations $P_i\psi = \pm\psi$ for several Pauli operators P_i precisely when these operators commute pairwise.

2.4 Clifford gates and the Gottesman–Knill setting

We now restrict attention to the circuits⁵ built from the gate set

$$\{X, Y, Z, H \text{ (Hadamard)}, S \text{ (Phase)}, \text{CNOT (Controlled NOT)}\}$$

together with computational-basis preparations and Pauli measurements.

All the gates listed above are called *Clifford gates*⁶. Unlike X, Y , and Z , the gates H, S , and CNOT are not Pauli operators, but they still preserve Pauli operators under conjugation. That is, for each such gate U and each $P \in P_n$, one has $UPU^\dagger \in P_n$. Here the gate acts on states by $\psi \mapsto U\psi$, whereas Pauli operators are tracked by $P \mapsto UPU^\dagger$. This is what makes the later binary description possible. The Gottesman–Knill theorem says that circuits using only Clifford gates, computational-basis preparations, and Pauli measurements can be sampled efficiently.[1, p. 19][2, p. 2]

3 Pauli labels and the symplectic form over \mathbb{F}_2

To study commutation without multiplying large matrices directly, we represent n -qubit Pauli operators, up to global phase, by binary vectors. This turns commutation into a bilinear test over \mathbb{F}_2 .

3.1 Binary labels for n -qubit Pauli operators

Since multiplying a Pauli operator by ± 1 or $\pm i$ does not affect its commutation relations, we work modulo global phase $\{\pm 1, \pm i\}$. On each qubit, once global phase is ignored, the four Pauli possibilities are represented by $I, X,$

⁵Here a circuit means a finite sequence of gates and Pauli measurements acting on one or more qubits; its length is the number of such steps.

⁶Their explicit matrix forms are recorded in Appendix B.

Z , and XZ (since $Y = iXZ$). After ignoring global phase, every such Pauli operator has a representative of the form $P = X^a Z^b$, $a, b \in \mathbb{F}_2^n$, where

$$X^a := X^{a_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes X^{a_n}, \quad Z^b := Z^{b_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes Z^{b_n},$$

with exponents taken in \mathbb{F}_2 . Let $V := \mathbb{F}_2^{2n} \cong \mathbb{F}_2^n \oplus \mathbb{F}_2^n$, and write $(a | b) \in V$ for the concatenation of a and b . Define the label map

$$\pi(X^a Z^b) := (a | b).$$

This is the standard phase-forgetting⁷ binary encoding of Pauli operators.[5, p. 11][3, pp. 1–2] We use the standard \mathbb{F}_2 dot product

$$a \cdot b := \sum_{j=1}^n a_j b_j \in \mathbb{F}_2.$$

For a second Pauli operator we similarly write $X^{a'} Z^{b'}$ with $a', b' \in \mathbb{F}_2^n$. The only multiplication fact we need is the sign obtained when commuting Z past X on the same qubit: $ZX = -XZ$. Hence for $a', b \in \mathbb{F}_2^n$,

$$Z^b X^{a'} = (-1)^{ba'} X^{a'} Z^b,$$

because a minus sign appears exactly when Z and X occur in the same tensor position, that is, when $b_j = a'_j = 1$; the parity of these positions is precisely $b \cdot a'$ in \mathbb{F}_2 . Therefore

$$(X^a Z^b)(X^{a'} Z^{b'}) = (-1)^{ba' + b'a} (X^{a'} Z^{b'})(X^a Z^b), \quad (1)$$

still ignoring global phase. [3, pp. 1–2]

3.2 Commutation via a symplectic form

Definition 3.2.1 (Symplectic form on $V = \mathbb{F}_2^{2n}$). For $v = (a | b)$ and $w = (a' | b')$ in V , define

$$\omega(v, w) := a \cdot b' + b \cdot a' \in \mathbb{F}_2.$$

The form ω is \mathbb{F}_2 -bilinear and satisfies $\omega(v, v) = 0$ for all v . [6, p. 2].

Proposition 3.2.2 (Commutation test). *Let $P = X^a Z^b$ and $Q = X^{a'} Z^{b'}$ be n -qubit Pauli operators (ignoring global phase). Then*

$$PQ = (-1)^{\omega(\pi(P), \pi(Q))} QP,$$

in particular $PQ = QP$ if and only if $\omega(\pi(P), \pi(Q)) = 0$. [6, pp. 1–2].

Proof. By (1), the commutation sign exponent is $b \cdot a' + b' \cdot a$. By Definition 3.2.1, this equals $\omega((a | b), (a' | b')) = \omega(\pi(P), \pi(Q))$. \square

⁷Here “phase-forgetting” means that Pauli operators differing only by a global phase in $\{\pm 1, \pm i\}$ are treated as the same in this encoding. This meaning will be used throughout.

4 Stabilizers as commuting Pauli constraints

To specify an n -qubit state, represented by a vector ψ , without listing its 2^n coefficients in the computational basis, we will describe it by Pauli conditions of the form $g\psi = \psi$. Equivalently, ψ lies in the +1 eigenspace⁸ of each chosen Pauli operator g . For these conditions to make sense together, the chosen Pauli operators must *commute*: if $gh = -hg$ and $g\psi = h\psi = \psi$, then $gh\psi = \psi$ but also $gh\psi = -\psi$, impossible for a nonzero state. This leads to the stabilizer definition: it is the abelian subgroup of Pauli operators whose common +1 eigenspace is exactly the state/subspace we want.[4, p. 18]

4.1 Stabilizer groups

Let \mathcal{P}_n denotes the n -qubit Pauli group⁹ (including phases), and that in the previous section commutation of Pauli operators was reduced to a bilinear test on binary labels.

Definition 4.1.1 (Stabilizer subgroup). A subgroup $S \leq \mathcal{P}_n$ is a *stabilizer subgroup* if it is abelian and $-I \notin S$. [4, p. 18] For such S , define the stabilized subspace

$$H_S := \{\psi \in (\mathbb{C}^2)^{\otimes n} : g\psi = \psi \text{ for all } g \in S\}.$$

Remark 4.1.2. If S is abelian and $-I \notin S$, then every $g \in S$ has order 2: indeed $g^2 \in \{\pm I\}$ for Pauli operators, and $g^2 = -I$ would force $-I \in S$. Hence S is an elementary abelian 2-group, so $S \cong (\mathbb{F}_2)^k$ for some k ; in particular, $|S| = 2^k$.

4.2 Dimension formula

Lemma 4.2.1 (Traces of Pauli operators). For $n \geq 1$, $\text{tr}(I) = 2^n$ and $\text{tr}(P) = 0$ for every Pauli $P \in \mathcal{P}_n$ with $P \neq \pm I$.

Proof. For one qubit, $\text{tr}(X) = \text{tr}(Y) = \text{tr}(Z) = 0$. For n qubits, $\text{tr}(A \otimes B) = \text{tr}(A)\text{tr}(B)$, so any tensor product with at least one traceless factor is traceless. The only Pauli operators with nonzero trace are $\pm I$. \square

Proposition 4.2.2 (Projector onto H_S). Let S be a stabilizer subgroup. Define

$$\Pi_S = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{g \in S} g.$$

Then Π_S is the orthogonal projector onto H_S . [5, pp. 8–9, 11].

⁸The +1 eigenspace of g is $E_+(g) = \{\psi \in \mathcal{H} : g\psi = \psi\}$.

⁹That is, $P_n := \{\alpha(P_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes P_n) : \alpha \in \{\pm 1, \pm i\}, P_j \in \{I, X, Y, Z\} \text{ for each } j\}$.

Proof. Since each $g \in P_n$ is unitary and S is closed under inverses, $\Pi_S^\dagger = \Pi_S$, so Π_S is Hermitian. To show that $\Pi_S^2 = \Pi_S$, compute

$$\Pi_S^2 = \frac{1}{|S|^2} \sum_{g,h \in S} gh = \frac{1}{|S|^2} \sum_{k \in S} \sum_{h \in S} k = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{k \in S} k = \Pi_S,$$

where for each fixed $h \in S$, right multiplication by h is a bijection $S \rightarrow S$, so as g ranges over S , the product $k = gh$ also ranges over all of S .

If $\psi \in H_S$, then $g\psi = \psi$ for all $g \in S$, hence $\Pi_S\psi = \psi$. Conversely, if $\Pi_S\psi = \psi$, then for any $s \in S$,

$$s\Pi_S = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{g \in S} sg = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{g \in S} g = \Pi_S$$

since S is a group, hence $s\psi = s\Pi_S\psi = \Pi_S\psi = \psi$. Therefore the image of Π_S is exactly H_S . Also, $\Pi_S^2 = \Pi_S$ shows that Π_S is a projection onto its image, while $\Pi_S^\dagger = \Pi_S$ shows that this projection is orthogonal (proof see Appendix A). Hence Π_S is the orthogonal projector onto H_S . \square

Corollary 4.2.3 (Dimension formula). *If $S \cong (\mathbb{F}_2)^k$, then $\dim H_S = 2^{n-k}$.*

Proof. By Proposition 4.2.2, $\dim H_S = \text{rank}(\Pi_S) = \text{tr}(\Pi_S)$. Using Lemma 4.2.1,

$$\text{tr}(\Pi_S) = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{g \in S} \text{tr}(g) = \frac{1}{|S|} \text{tr}(I) = \frac{2^n}{|S|} = 2^{n-k}.$$

\square

4.3 Uniqueness of stabilizer states

A generating set $\{g_1, \dots, g_k\} \subseteq S$ is called *independent* if the only product

$$g_1^{x_1} \cdots g_k^{x_k} = I \quad (x_i \in \mathbb{F}_2)$$

is $x_1 = \cdots = x_k = 0$. Equivalently, the map $\mathbb{F}_2^k \rightarrow S$, $x \mapsto \prod_i g_i^{x_i}$ is an isomorphism, so $|S| = 2^k$. Thus, by Corollary 4.2.3, if S has n independent generators, then $\dim H_S = 1$, so H_S is spanned by a unique state up to global phase; such a state is called a *stabilizer state*. [4, p. 18]

5 Clifford gates and the induced symplectic action

5.1 Clifford group and its action on Pauli labels

Definition 5.1.1 (Clifford group). The n -qubit Clifford group is [6, p. 2]

$$\mathcal{C}_n := \{U \in U(2^n) : U\mathcal{P}_n U^\dagger = \mathcal{P}_n\}.$$
¹⁰

¹⁰Here $U(2^n)$ denotes the group of all $2^n \times 2^n$ unitary complex matrices.

Fix the phase-forgetting Pauli parametrization from the previous section: every Pauli operator (modulo global phase) is represented as $X^a Z^b$ with label $\pi(X^a Z^b) = (a | b) \in V = \mathbb{F}_2^{2n}$ [5, p. 11]. For $U \in \mathcal{C}_n$ and $v \in V$, define $F_U(v) \in V$ by the requirement

$$\pi(U P(v) U^\dagger) = F_U(v),$$

where $P(v)$ denotes any Pauli representative with label v , which is well-defined since π forgets global phase. In words, $F_U(v)$ is the label of the Pauli operator obtained by conjugating a Pauli operator with label v by U .

Theorem 5.1.2 (Clifford induces a symplectic transformation). *For each $U \in \mathcal{C}_n$, the induced map $F_U : V \rightarrow V$ is \mathbb{F}_2 -linear and satisfies [6, p. 2]*

$$\omega(F_U v, F_U w) = \omega(v, w) \quad \text{for all } v, w \in V.$$

Hence F_U is an invertible \mathbb{F}_2 -linear map preserving ω .

Proof. We prove separately that F_U is \mathbb{F}_2 -linear and that it preserves the symplectic form ω .

(*Linearity*) In the phase-forgetting Pauli group, multiplication corresponds to addition of labels: $\pi(P(v)P(w)) = v + w$. Conjugation by U preserves multiplication of Pauli operators (modulo phase), so

$$F_U(v+w) = \pi(UP(v)P(w)U^\dagger) = \pi(UP(v)U^\dagger \cdot UP(w)U^\dagger) = F_U(v) + F_U(w),$$

and $F_U(0) = 0$, hence F_U is \mathbb{F}_2 -linear.

(*Symplecticity*) For Pauli representatives $P(v), P(w)$ we have

$$P(v)P(w) = (-1)^{\omega(v,w)} P(w)P(v).$$

Conjugating by U preserves this commutation sign:

$$\begin{aligned} UP(v)U^\dagger UP(w)U^\dagger &= UP(v)P(w)U^\dagger = (-1)^{\omega(v,w)} UP(w)P(v)U^\dagger \\ &= (-1)^{\omega(v,w)} UP(w)U^\dagger UP(v)U^\dagger. \end{aligned}$$

Applying π , the Pauli operator $UP(v)U^\dagger$ has label $F_U(v)$ and similarly for w . Hence the sign is determined by $\omega(F_U(v), F_U(w))$. Therefore $\omega(F_U v, F_U w) = \omega(v, w)$. \square

5.2 Label updates for H , S , and CNOT

For the later tableau simulation, we now make the induced maps F_U from Theorem 5.1.2 explicit for the generating Clifford gates H , S , and CNOT, by

writing down how each gate updates a label $v = (a | b) \in V$. For the Pauli gates X , Y , and Z , conjugation by a Pauli gate changes only the global phase, so the phase-forgetting label is unchanged; therefore we only need explicit label updates for H , S , and CNOT. (The conjugation identities used later are verified in Appendix B)

Single-qubit gates. On a single qubit, the Hadamard gate H acts by conjugation as $HXH^\dagger = Z$ and $HZH^\dagger = X$, while the phase gate S satisfies $SZS^\dagger = Z$ and $SXS^\dagger = XZ$ up to phase. Thus, in the label $(a | b)$, the gate H interchanges a and b , whereas S leaves a unchanged and replaces b by $a + b$. In labels $(a | b) \in \mathbb{F}_2^2$ this is

$$F_H : (a | b) \mapsto (b | a), \quad F_S : (a | b) \mapsto (a | a + b).$$

On n qubits, applying H (or S) on qubit j applies the same update only to the j th components of (a, b) , leaving all others unchanged.[1, p. 4][4, p. 41]

Two-qubit CNOT. For distinct qubits c and t , write $U = \text{CNOT}_{c \rightarrow t}$. Here X_c means that X acts on the c th qubit and the identity acts on every other qubit; similarly for X_t , Z_c , and Z_t . The following identities describe how a Pauli operator changes when it is moved past the gate $U = \text{CNOT}_{c \rightarrow t}$:

$$UX_cU^\dagger = X_cX_t, \quad UX_tU^\dagger = X_t, \quad UZ_cU^\dagger = Z_c, \quad UZ_tU^\dagger = Z_cZ_t.$$

Thus U sends X_c to X_cX_t , meaning that an X on the c -th qubit becomes an X on both the c -th and t -th qubits; similarly, U sends Z_t to Z_cZ_t , and leaves X_t and Z_c unchanged. Equivalently, if $v = (a | b) \in \mathbb{F}_2^{2n}$ is the label of a Pauli operator, then

$$a_t \leftarrow a_t + a_c, \quad b_c \leftarrow b_c + b_t,$$

Here \leftarrow means “replace by”. In this form, the X -entry at t is updated by adding the old X -entry at c , and similarly for Z . [1, p. 4][4, p. 41]

6 A proof of the Gottesman–Knill theorem

In the previous sections, we rewrote Pauli operators and their commutation relations in binary symplectic language, and saw that a stabilizer state can be specified by commuting generators rather than by all 2^n amplitudes. We now use this description to build a classical simulation procedure: the state will be stored by a tableau, and each gate or measurement will be handled by updating this finite binary data instead of a full state vector.

6.1 Tableau representation

A stabilizer state on n qubits is specified by n independent commuting Pauli constraints $g_i\psi = \psi$. Since the generators g_i commute and are independent, Corollary 4.2.3 with $k = n$ shows that their common $+1$ eigenspace has dimension $2^{n-n} = 1$, so they determine a unique stabilizer state up to global phase. We store a generating set $\{g_1, \dots, g_n\}$ via their phase-forgetting labels

$$v_i := \pi(g_i) \in V = \mathbb{F}_2^{2n}, \quad v_i = (a_i \mid b_i),$$

as the rows of a binary matrix

$$T = (v_1, \dots, v_n)^\top \in \mathbb{F}_2^{n \times 2n}.$$

To record the ± 1 eigenvalue of each generator, we store an additional sign vector $r \in \mathbb{F}_2^n$ such that the i th row represents the constraint

$$(-1)^{r_i} P(v_i)\psi = \psi,$$

where $P(v_i)$ is any Pauli representative with label v_i (global phases $\pm i$ are ignored throughout). The label v_i records only the Pauli type after phase is forgotten, so $P(v_i)$ and $-P(v_i)$ have the same label. However, the constraints $P(v_i)\psi = \psi$ and $P(v_i)\psi = -\psi$ are different, so the extra bit r_i is needed to record which sign occurs. Thus the pair (v_i, r_i) encodes the signed generator $g_i = (-1)^{r_i} P(v_i)$.

Row operations change the generating set but not the stabilized state:

$$v_i \leftarrow v_i + v_j \iff g_i \leftarrow g_i g_j.$$

This is the basic tableau row operation used in efficient stabilizer simulation: after forgetting phase, multiplication of Paulis corresponds to addition of labels, so $\pi(g_i g_j) = \pi(g_i) + \pi(g_j) = v_i + v_j$; and if $g_i\psi = \psi$ and $g_j\psi = \psi$, then $(g_i g_j)\psi = g_i(g_j\psi) = g_i\psi = \psi$, so replacing g_i by $g_i g_j$ changes the generating set but not the stabilized state. [2, pp. 3–4]

Once the tableau has been set up, each later step in the circuit is of one of two types: if the step is a Clifford gate, we use the tableau update from Section 6.2; if the step is a measurement of a Pauli operator, we use the tableau update from Section 6.3. These are two alternative cases for a single step, not two updates performed simultaneously.

6.2 Tableau update under Clifford gates

The point of storing the state by the tableau (T, r) is that, instead of updating a vector in a 2^n -dimensional space, we only need to update the generators

$g_i = (-1)^{r_i} P(v_i)$ that determine the stabilizer state. If U is a Clifford gate and the current state ψ is stabilized by g_1, \dots, g_n , then after applying U the new state is $\psi' = U\psi$. For each generator g_i we have $g_i\psi = \psi$, hence

$$(Ug_iU^\dagger)\psi' = (Ug_iU^\dagger)(U\psi) = Ug_i\psi = U\psi = \psi'.$$

Thus Ug_iU^\dagger stabilizes the new state. Since U is a Clifford gate, conjugation still sends Pauli operators to Pauli operators, so a stabilizer $\langle g_1, \dots, g_n \rangle$ updates as

$$\langle g_1, \dots, g_n \rangle \mapsto \langle Ug_1U^\dagger, \dots, Ug_nU^\dagger \rangle.$$

Equivalently, on labels we have an induced \mathbb{F}_2 -linear map F_U preserving ω and update each row by

$$v_i \leftarrow F_U(v_i).$$

This is exactly the “track the generators under conjugation” rule.

For the generating gate set H, S, CNOT we use the explicit label updates from the previous section. For the Pauli gates X, Y , and Z , the phase-forgetting label does not change under conjugation. Indeed, if $U = P(u)$ is a Pauli gate, then $UP(v)U^\dagger = (-1)^{\omega(u,v)}P(v)$, so $F_U(v) = v$. Hence in the tableau these gates leave each row label v_i unchanged and only modify the sign bit r_i . Implementationally, this means updating all n rows of the tableau, each of length $2n$, so the classical tableau update for a single gate takes $O(n^2)$ elementary binary operations.¹¹[2, p. 3]

6.3 Tableau update under Pauli measurement

Let the current stabilizer be stored by (T, r) and suppose we measure a Pauli operator

$$M = P(m), \quad m = (a \mid b) \in V, \quad a, b \in \mathbb{F}_2^n,$$

where $P(m) = X^a Z^b$ [5, p. 11]. Since M is Hermitian with eigenvalues ± 1 , its $+1$ and -1 eigenspaces are orthogonal, and $(I \pm M)/2$ are the corresponding orthogonal projectors, where I is the identity operator. There are two cases: M commutes with every stabilizer generator, or it anti-commutes with at least one generator[5, pp. 8–9].

Compute the commutation pattern [6, p. 2]

$$s_i := \omega(v_i, m) \in \mathbb{F}_2 \quad (i = 1, \dots, n).$$

¹¹Here $O(n^2)$ refers to the time complexity of the update.

Case 1: commuting. If $s_i = 0$ for all i , then M commutes with every generator. Since the current stabilizer state ψ spans a one-dimensional common eigenspace of these generators, M preserves that line and acts on it by ± 1 ; equivalently, either $M\psi = \psi$ or $M\psi = -\psi$, and hence either $M \in S$ or $-M \in S$. Therefore the measurement outcome, the eigenvalue returned by measuring M , is deterministic: if $M\psi = \psi$ the outcome is $+1$, and if $M\psi = -\psi$ the outcome is -1 . In either case the projection leaves the state on the same one-dimensional line, so the post-measurement stabilizer is unchanged.[1, p. 15][2, pp. 3–4]

Algorithmically, it only remains to determine whether this is $+M$ or $-M$, which we do by solving the linear system over \mathbb{F}_2

$$x^\top T = m^\top,$$

that is, finding $x = (x_1, \dots, x_n)^\top \in \mathbb{F}_2^n$ such that $m = x_1 v_1 + \dots + x_n v_n$, where $x_i = 1$ means that the generator g_i is included in the product and $x_i = 0$ means that it is not. The corresponding product $g_1^{x_1} \dots g_n^{x_n}$ has label m , and since the i th stored generator is $(-1)^{r_i} P(v_i)$, its sign is $(-1)^{x_1 r_1 + \dots + x_n r_n}$. Thus the same coefficients x_i applied to the stored r bits determine whether the product is $+M$ or $-M$. Output the forced outcome and leave (T, r) unchanged.

Case 2: anti-commuting. If some $s_i = 1$, pick one such index as a pivot (call it p). By multiplying generators, we may assume (without loss of generality) that M anti-commutes with exactly one generator and commutes with the rest; more explicitly, perform row operations so that

$$s_p = 1, \quad s_j = 0 \ (j \neq p),$$

by applying, for each $j \neq p$ with $s_j = 1$, the row update $v_j \leftarrow v_j + v_p$ (and the corresponding sign-bit update), which corresponds to replacing g_j by $g_j g_p$; since both g_j and g_p anti-commute with M , the new generator commutes with M , equivalently $\omega(v_j + v_p, m) = \omega(v_j, m) + \omega(v_p, m) = 1 + 1 = 0$ in \mathbb{F}_2 .

In this case the measurement outcome is unbiased:[1, p. 15][2, pp. 3–4]

$$p(+1) = p(-1) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad p(\pm 1) \text{ denotes the corresponding probability.}$$

Indeed, let $\Pi_\pm = (I \pm M)/2$. Since $g_p M = -M g_p$, we have $g_p(I \pm M) = g_p \pm g_p M = g_p \mp M g_p = (I \mp M)g_p$, hence $g_p \Pi_\pm = \Pi_\mp g_p$. Using $g_p \psi = \psi$, this gives $g_p \Pi_\pm \psi = \Pi_\mp \psi$; since g_p is unitary, $\|\Pi_+ \psi\| = \|\Pi_- \psi\|$. Hence the two outcomes occur with equal probability.

If the outcome is $+1$, then the post-measurement state is $\tilde{\psi} = \Pi_+\psi/\|\Pi_+\psi\|$, which satisfies $M\tilde{\psi} = \tilde{\psi}$ and $g_j\tilde{\psi} = \tilde{\psi}$ for all $j \neq p$, so the new stabilizer is obtained by replacing the pivot generator by $+M$. Similarly, if the outcome is -1 , then the post-measurement state is $\tilde{\psi} = \Pi_-\psi/\|\Pi_-\psi\|$, so the new stabilizer is obtained by replacing the pivot generator by $-M$.

Algorithmically: since the two outcomes occur with equal probability, sample one of them at random and encode it by $\beta \in \mathbb{F}_2$, then set

$$v_p \leftarrow m, \quad r_p \leftarrow \beta,$$

so that the pivot row now represents $(-1)^\beta P(m)$, that is, $+M$ if $\beta = 0$ and $-M$ if $\beta = 1$, and keep all other rows as after the commutation-fixing row operations above.

All the above uses only \mathbb{F}_2 linear algebra on (T, r) plus evaluations of ω , so the classical tableau update for a single Pauli measurement costs $O(n^2)$.

6.4 Statement and proof of Gottesman–Knill theorem

Theorem 6.4.1 (Gottesman–Knill). *Suppose a quantum computation involves only: preparations in the computational basis; Hadamard, phase, controlled-NOT, and the Pauli gates X, Y, Z ; and measurements of Pauli operators (possibly adaptive, with classical control). Then its measurement outcome distribution can be classically sampled in polynomial time in n and the circuit length m (in particular, $O(n^2m)$ using generator-tracking updates). [1, p. 19][2, p. 2]*

Proof. We simulate the computation step-by-step, maintaining a tableau (T, r) for a generating set of the current stabilizer.

1. Initialization. For $e_0^{\otimes n}$, take generators Z_1, \dots, Z_n and set $r = 0$. This is because $Ze_0 = e_0$, so each Z_i fixes the initial state $e_0^{\otimes n}$. Hence these commuting generators describe the initial stabilizer exactly.

2. Unitary gates. For each allowed gate U , update each row label by $v_i \leftarrow F_U(v_i)$, yielding the correct conjugated generators Ug_iU^\dagger . Indeed, if $g_i\psi = \psi$, then $(Ug_iU^\dagger)(U\psi) = U(g_i\psi) = U\psi$, so Ug_iU^\dagger stabilizes the evolved state $U\psi$.

3. Measurements. For a measurement of a Pauli operator M , apply the update from Section 6.3. If M commutes with the stabilizer, then M preserves the one-dimensional stabilized subspace, so it acts there by ± 1 ; hence the outcome is forced and the tableau is unchanged. If M anti-commutes with some generator, row operations reduce to a single pivot g_p ,

and replacing g_p by the measured Pauli with the observed sign gives the post-measurement stabilizer.

By induction over the circuit operations, the simulator maintains a tableau describing the same stabilizer constraints as the quantum state after each step, and samples outcomes with the correct probabilities. Each update uses $O(n^2)$ elementary \mathbb{F}_2 operations on $2n$ -bit rows, so m operations total $O(n^2m)$ classical time. \square

7 Conclusion

The essay began with a simple question: if an n -qubit state lives in a space of dimension 2^n , why can some quantum circuits still be simulated efficiently? The answer is that, for stabilizer circuits, the relevant information can be encoded by symplectic linear algebra over \mathbb{F}_2 : Pauli operators become binary vectors, commutation is controlled by a symplectic form, Clifford gates become symplectic linear maps, and Pauli measurements become tableau updates. This allows the computation to be tracked without storing a full state vector.

The same symplectic framework also underlies stabilizer codes and quantum error correction.[3, p. 1][2, p. 2][4, pp. 40–41] So the theorem is not only a simulation result, but part of a wider algebraic structure in stabilizer theory.

References

- [1] D. Gottesman, *The Heisenberg Representation of Quantum Computers*, (1998). [arXiv:quant-ph/9807006](#).
- [2] S. Aaronson and D. Gottesman, *Improved Simulation of Stabilizer Circuits*, *Physical Review A* **70**, 052328 (2004). [arXiv:quant-ph/0406196](#).
- [3] J. Dehaene and B. De Moor, *Clifford group, stabilizer states, and linear and quadratic operations over $GF(2)$* , *Physical Review A* **68**, 042318 (2003). [arXiv:quant-ph/0304125](#).
- [4] D. Gottesman, *Stabilizer Codes and Quantum Error Correction*, Ph.D. thesis, California Institute of Technology (1997). [arXiv:quant-ph/9705052](#).
- [5] D. Gottesman, *An Introduction to Quantum Error Correction*, (2000). [arXiv:quant-ph/0004072](#).
- [6] A. R. Calderbank, E. M. Rains, P. W. Shor, and N. J. A. Sloane, *Quantum Error Correction and Orthogonal Geometry*, (1996). [arXiv:quant-ph/9605005](#).

A Auxiliary linear-algebra results used in the text

We record two standard linear-algebra facts used in the text, and the proof of Lemma 2.3.1.

1. **Hermitian criterion.** Let T be a linear operator on a finite-dimensional complex Hilbert space \mathcal{H} . Then T is Hermitian if and only if

$$\langle Tx, y \rangle = \langle x, Ty \rangle \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \mathcal{H}.$$

Indeed, if $T = T^\dagger$, then by the definition of the adjoint,

$$\langle Tx, y \rangle = \langle x, T^\dagger y \rangle = \langle x, Ty \rangle.$$

Conversely, if $\langle Tx, y \rangle = \langle x, Ty \rangle$ for all x, y , then also

$$\langle Tx, y \rangle = \langle x, T^\dagger y \rangle$$

by the definition of T^\dagger , so

$$\langle x, (T - T^\dagger)y \rangle = 0 \quad \text{for all } x, y \in \mathcal{H}.$$

Hence $(T - T^\dagger)y = 0$ for all y , and therefore $T = T^\dagger$.

2. **Proof of Lemma 2.3.1.** By the spectral theorem, since A is Hermitian, it has a decomposition into its eigenspaces as in Footnote 4. In particular, \mathcal{H} is an orthogonal direct sum of these eigenspaces:

$$\mathcal{H} = \bigoplus_{\lambda} E_{\lambda}, \quad E_{\lambda} = \text{Ker}(A - \lambda I).$$

For $v \in E_{\lambda}$, we have $Av = \lambda v$, and using $AB = BA$,

$$A(Bv) = B(Av) = B(\lambda v) = \lambda(Bv),$$

so $Bv \in E_{\lambda}$. Thus B maps each eigenspace E_{λ} into itself. Since $B(E_{\lambda}) \subseteq E_{\lambda}$, we may view B as an operator

$$B|_{E_{\lambda}}: E_{\lambda} \rightarrow E_{\lambda}.$$

By part (1), an operator is Hermitian exactly when

$$\langle Tx, y \rangle = \langle x, Ty \rangle \quad \text{for all } x, y.$$

Since B is Hermitian on \mathcal{H} , this identity in particular holds for all $u, v \in E_{\lambda}$, so $B|_{E_{\lambda}}$ is Hermitian. By the spectral theorem, it therefore

has an orthonormal basis of eigenvectors in E_λ . Each of these vectors already lies in E_λ , so it is also an eigenvector of A with eigenvalue λ . Doing this for each λ and then collecting all these basis vectors together gives an orthonormal basis of \mathcal{H} consisting of common eigenvectors of A and B .

3. **Orthogonal projector criterion.** Let P be a linear operator on \mathcal{H} such that $P^2 = P$ and $P^\dagger = P$. Then P is the orthogonal projector onto $\text{im}(P)$. Indeed, if $y \in \text{im}(P)$, then $y = Px$ for some x , so $Py = P^2x = Px = y$. Also every $x \in \mathcal{H}$ can be written as

$$x = Px + (x - Px),$$

with $Px \in \text{im}(P)$ and $x - Px \in \ker(P)$ because

$$P(x - Px) = Px - P^2x = 0.$$

If $y = Pu \in \text{im}(P)$ and $z \in \ker(P)$, then

$$\langle y, z \rangle = \langle Pu, z \rangle = \langle u, P^\dagger z \rangle = \langle u, Pz \rangle = 0.$$

Thus

$$\mathcal{H} = \text{im}(P) \oplus \ker(P)$$

is an orthogonal direct sum, and P acts as the identity on $\text{im}(P)$ and as 0 on $\ker(P)$. Hence P is the orthogonal projector onto $\text{im}(P)$. Applying this to $P = \Pi_S$, whose image is H_S by Proposition 4.2.2, gives the claim there.

B Explicit matrices for H , S , and CNOT

For convenience, we record the explicit matrices for the gates H , S , and CNOT used in Section 5.2, and verify the conjugation identities stated there.

For one qubit,

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad S = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i \end{pmatrix}.$$

A direct matrix multiplication gives

$$HXH^\dagger = Z, \quad HZH^\dagger = X,$$

and

$$SZS^\dagger = Z, \quad SXS^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = -iY = XZ \text{ up to global phase.}$$

For two qubits, with respect to the ordered basis

$$\{e_0 \otimes e_0, e_0 \otimes e_1, e_1 \otimes e_0, e_1 \otimes e_1\},$$

the gate $\text{CNOT}_{c \rightarrow t}$ is

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Writing

$$X_c = X \otimes I, \quad X_t = I \otimes X, \quad Z_c = Z \otimes I, \quad Z_t = I \otimes Z,$$

Since $U^\dagger = U$, one example is

$$UX_cU^\dagger = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = X_cX_t.$$

The other three identities are checked in exactly the same way:

$$UX_tU^\dagger = X_t, \quad UZ_cU^\dagger = Z_c, \quad UZ_tU^\dagger = Z_cZ_t.$$

These are exactly the identities used in Section 5.2.